

**Migrant
Integration through
Locally designed
Experiences**

The inclusion of migrants in policy making

A report on Ripollet, Spain

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents an examination of the incorporation of migrants in the formulation and implementation of local policies in the municipality of Ripollet, Spain. The study specifically focuses on evaluating the current state of equality, diversity, integration, and civic engagement policies and practices within the city, as well as analysing any progress that has been made in these areas over time.

The municipality of Ripollet is situated in the north-eastern region of Spain, in proximity to the coastal area. It is located in Province of Barcelona within the autonomous community of Catalonia. Catalonia has 42 political areas named *comarcas*, and Ripollet is located in the central region of the *comarca* Vallès Occidental. The municipality, as of 2022, has a population of 39,314 and an area of 4.39 square kilometers.

In the 1960s, Ripollet experienced a strong influx of newcomers, transforming the previously rural village with a population of less than 5,000 into an industrialized town with one of the highest rates of population growth in the province of Barcelona. The migration during this time period was primarily of Spanish, with 49% from the Barcelona and surrounding Catalonia region and 51% from the South of Spain: Andalusia and Extremadura. Additionally, more recent years have also seen a significant increase in population, with the most notable growth occurring between 1999 and 2009 during which the population grew by nearly 8,000 people. Although growth continues from 2010 onwards, it has been less substantial.

An analysis of the most recent data by the Catalan Statistical Institute pertaining to the migrant population in the municipality of Ripollet reveals that out of the 39,139 individuals residing in Ripollet in 2021, 6,307 were foreign-born citizens and 4,835 were individuals with foreign nationalities. An examination of more recent data from the municipality of Ripollet in 2022, shows that out of the 39,314 inhabitants living in Ripollet a total of 17,737 international migrants were recorded as residing in the area. This data included second-generation migrants who were born in Spain but do not possess Spanish citizenship. However, it should be noted that the data gathered by Ripollet municipality on the migrant population is varied and not entirely consistent.

In the year 2022, a demographic analysis of the migrant population registered in the municipality of Ripollet revealed the largest proportion were of Moroccan origin, with a total of 2,898 people. This was followed by a significant presence of 1,483 from Pakistan and 1,431 from Romania.

The political party in control of the municipality of Ripollet is called *Ara Decidim Ripollet*. This party holds office since 2019 until 2023. Ara Decidim Ripollet is a coalition of left-wing parties and organizations focusing on four main areas in their political agenda: social justice and social rights, community development, economic development, and democracy for all.

The economy of Ripollet is primarily based on the service sector, which employs 72.2% of the population, followed by industry (19.1%) and construction (8.7%). The metal sector is a notable local specialty, as well as furniture and logistics. The unemployment rate in Ripollet is average at 11.5%, slightly under the Spanish one that is on average 12%.

Ripollet does not have any official organization run by migrants, but various non-governmental organizations work in support of migrants and in partnership with the local government.

The municipality of Ripollet adheres to the migration policies established by the Spanish government. There are no specific policies tailored to the needs of migrants within the municipality. However, the Educational Department of the municipality has implemented an Educational Plan which indirectly supports the migrant population. This plan aims to facilitate the integration of newcomers into the educational system by providing services for the study and comprehension of the Catalan language. Additionally, it ensures that children and adolescents are seamlessly integrated into the city's educational system upon their arrival, in order to protect their educational rights.

The municipality of Ripollet does not have explicit policies to promote diversity and equal opportunities for migrants. However, the city promotes an understanding of migration through historical memory and educational initiatives. The city has a specific memory program called "Memory=Dignity" which aims to prevent human rights violations and promote democracy through education about migration history. Since 2018, the city organises an annual [event](#) to present past human rights violations in the municipality with a focus on dictatorship, exiles from Ripollet, and the Spanish Civil War.

The municipality of Ripollet has a well-established tradition of civic participation, which was initiated in 1980 with the formation of various municipal councils for the purpose of discussing and managing cultural, work, sport, school, and social services within the municipality. In 2021, the municipality further solidified its commitment to civic engagement by developing the *Reglament de Participació*, which outlines various mechanisms for citizen participation. This regulation emphasizes the importance of cultural diversity and a gender perspective in all participatory activities and encourages the active involvement of all members of the community. While no specific participatory practices are currently in place for migrants, the municipality is actively engaged in research and development through its participation in the MILE project to investigate and implement new guidelines for the inclusion of this population.

The municipality of Ripollet has implemented various strategies to promote citizen participation and reduce social and political distance with the population. This includes the establishment of a television and radio channels, as well as the utilisation of formal and informal consultation platforms, citizen forums, and a monthly newspaper. However, these efforts organised from a top-down perspective do not take into account the diversity of languages spoken in the area, which may pose a barrier to participation for migrants.

1 THE LOCAL AND NATIONAL CONTEXT OF MIGRATION

1.1 The municipality context

Ripollet is located in the north-eastern part of Spain, close to the coast. Ripollet is a municipality in the Province of Barcelona. Barcelona is located in Catalonia which is one of the 17 autonomous communities of Spain. Catalonia is divided into 42 *comarcas*¹, and Ripollet² is located in the centre of the comarca Vallès Occidental. It borders to the north with Barberà del Vallès, southwest with Cerdanyola del Vallès and southeast with Montcada and Reixac.

Spain has a population of 47.4 million. The total number of men is 23.2 million while the total number of women is 24.2 million. The municipality of Ripollet has a total population of 39,314 (2022), on the surface of 4.39 km², of which 19,434 (49.4%) are women (average age 39 years) and 19,880 (50.6%) are men (average age: 42 years).³

The population of Ripollet has followed a dynamic growth in the last 60 years. According to the *Report of the Map of the Cultural Heritage of Ripollet*⁴ of 2009, the strong flow of 'newcomers'⁵ happened in the 1960's, transforming a rural village with little more than 5,000 inhabitants into an industrial town with one of the indexes of the highest population growth in the province of Barcelona. During the 1960's, migration has been at a national level, with 49% of internal migrants⁶ from Barcelona and around Catalonia and 51% of external migrants⁷ from the region of Andalusia and from the region of Extremadura.⁸

Recently, the most significant increase occurred between 1999 and 2009, a period in which the population grew by almost 8,000 people. From 2010 onwards, growth continues, but less significantly.⁹ Two demographic phenomena can explain the recent

¹ Comarcas are groups of municipalities, roughly equivalent to counties in the US or districts in the UK.

² Diputació de Barcelona (2021) Pla local d'habitatge, Fase 3. Document final. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/habitatge/pla-local-dhabitatge/accés-al-document-integre-del-pla-local-dhabitatge-sotmpes-a-informacio-publica/pla-local-dhabitatge-ripollet-document-dexposicio-publica.pdf/@@download/file/Pla%20Local%20d'Habitatge%20Ripollet.%20Document%20d'exposicio%20C3%B3%20p%C3%BAblica.pdf> [Accessed on 20/06/2022]

³ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022) Dades demogràfiques, de situació i clima de Ripollet. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/ciutat/el-municipi/dades-basiques> [Accessed on 24/11/2022]

⁴ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2009) Mapa del Patrimoni Cultural de Ripollet Memòria tècnica. Available at: <https://patrimonicultural.diba.cat/sites/default/files/mapes/grups/adjunts/08180.pdf> [Accessed on 30/06/2022]

⁵ Council define newcomers as people who come from outside Ripollet including national and international migrants.

⁶ Migrants coming from Catalonia region.

⁷ Migrants coming from outside Catalonia but not from outside Spain.

⁸ Garcia M, Domenech (2007) Històries compartides. La immigració dels anys seixanta i noranta a Ripollet, Ed. EMA Publicacions, Ripollet.

⁹ Diputació de Barcelona (2021) Pla local d'habitatge, Fase 3. Document final. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/habitatge/pla-local-dhabitatge/accés-al-document-integre-del-pla-local-dhabitatge-sotmpes-a-informacio-publica/pla-local-dhabitatge-ripollet-document-dexposicio-publica.pdf/@@download/file/Pla%20Local%20d'Habitatge%20Ripollet.%20Document%20d'exposicio%20C3%B3%20p%C3%BAblica.pdf>

increase in population: natural growth¹⁰ and migrant movements. In the last 20 years, natural growth has been positive. The natural growth has been particularly high from 2004 to 2009, with a balance of over +300 people per year. Since 2011, the growth has steadily declined, reaching less than 100 people in 2017 and 2018. So, the demographic increase in Ripollet cannot be explained exclusively by natural growth.

Population changes over the last few years have also been influenced by migration. Between 2011 and 2021, the net migration to Ripollet was often negative; for example, in 2021 (-51), 2020 (-50), 2013 (-92), 2012 (-281) and 2011 (-119), however, net migration was also significantly positive for some years, including 2019 (+487), 2018 (+329), 2017 (+440), 2016 (+128), 2015 (+64) and 2014 (+60).¹¹

Ripollet has a population density of 8,929 inhabitants / km², which is much higher than the Vallès Occidental average of 1,586 inhabitants / km² and slightly higher than Barcelona city, which has population density of 8,003 inhabitants / km². According to the 2016 Urban Mobility Plan, 86% of Ripollet's population lives in the main urban core, with the neighbourhoods of Can Mas and Can Clos being the most densely populated (24% and 24%, respectively). 14% of the total population is concentrated in the Can Tiana-Pont Vell neighbourhood¹².

The municipality offers several publicly funded services that can be summarized in three categories: Education, Health and Culture. There are 6 kindergartens or nursery schools, 11 schools of primary education and 3 high schools, located throughout the territory. There are also 3 Primary Care Centres in the municipality. Ripollet has a large number of cultural centres spread around the entire town. These centres are not specifically created to foster dialogue between migrant communities and locals, but they are used and visited by migrant communities.

The political party that is leading the municipality of Ripollet is *Ara Decidim Ripollet* (Now we decide Ripollet) whose mandate began in 2019 and will end in 2023. *Ara Decidim Ripollet* is a coalition of left-wing parties and political organizations including COP, Podemos, Catalonia en Comu. The political stance is left-leaning, emphasizing that "life and people are at the center" of their programmes. There are 4 main areas of action defined in their political programme: (1) Social Justice and Social rights; (2) Social Justice

[dhabitatge-sotmpes-a-informacio-publica/pla-local-dhabitatge-ripollet-document-dexposicio-publica.pdf/@_@_download/file/Pla%20Local%20d'Habitatge%20Ripollet.%20Document%20d'exposicio%20C3%B3%20p%20C3%BAblica.pdf](https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/habitatge/pla-local-dhabitatge/acces-al-document-integre-del-pla-local-dhabitatge-sotmpes-a-informacio-publica/pla-local-dhabitatge-ripollet-document-dexposicio-publica.pdf/@_@_download/file/Pla%20Local%20d'Habitatge%20Ripollet.%20Document%20d'exposicio%20C3%B3%20p%20C3%BAblica.pdf) [Accessed on 20/06/2022]

¹⁰ The difference between births and deaths in a specific arc of time.

¹¹ Idescat (2021) Migracions. Totals. Available at:

<https://www.idescat.cat/pub/?id=mm&n=5489&geo=mun:081803&lang=es> [Accessed on 21/11/2022]

¹² Diputació de Barcelona (2021) Pla local d'habitatge, Fase 3. Document final. Available at:

https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/habitatge/pla-local-dhabitatge/acces-al-document-integre-del-pla-local-dhabitatge-sotmpes-a-informacio-publica/pla-local-dhabitatge-ripollet-document-dexposicio-publica.pdf/@_@_download/file/Pla%20Local%20d'Habitatge%20Ripollet.%20Document%20d'exposicio%20C3%B3%20p%20C3%BAblica.pdf [Accessed on 20/06/2022]

and community development; (3) Social and Economic development; and (4) Democracy for all.

Residents of Ripollet work primarily in the service sector (72%), industry (19%) and construction (9%). The local specialism is the metal sector, followed by furniture and logistics.¹³

The unemployment rate in Spain is 12%, while in Ripollet it is around 11.5%. However, it should be noted that in Ripollet, and also throughout the county, the distribution of unemployment in terms of gender is not equal as women have an index of 59% in the country. The gender bias is significant.¹⁴

Catalonia is one of the most dynamic regions in Europe for entrepreneurial activity. Barcelona in particular is one of the top cities for start-up investment.¹⁵ Ripollet council does not currently provide in-depth information on its entrepreneurial activities in the area, but it intends to fill this gap by starting a territory's mapping process. There are a number of organisations in the municipality supporting business and entrepreneurial activity. Ripollet Impulsa¹⁶ offers services that enable companies and entrepreneurs to develop and consolidate their business operations, to understand the business environment and to improve their competitiveness. Ripollet municipality has several projects to support young entrepreneurs in the area, and a dedicated focus on metal entrepreneurship.¹⁷

1.2 Migrant population and migration history

1.2.1 Migrant population and migration trends

The municipality of Ripollet has 17,737 international migrants registered in the area. In 2022, the migrants registered in Ripollet were mainly from Morocco (2,898), Pakistan

¹³ Diputació de Barcelona (2021) Pla local d'habitatge, Fase 3. Document final. Available at: https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/habitatge/pla-local-dhabitatge/acces-al-document-integre-del-pla-local-dhabitatge-sotmpes-a-informacio-publica/pla-local-dhabitatge-ripollet-document-dexposicio-publica.pdf/@_@download/file/Pla%20Local%20d'Habitatge%20Ripollet.%20Document%20d'exposici%C3%B3%20p%C3%BAblica.pdf [Accessed on 20/06/2022]

¹⁴ Diputació de Barcelona (2021) Pla local d'habitatge, Fase 3. Document final. Available at: https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/habitatge/pla-local-dhabitatge/acces-al-document-integre-del-pla-local-dhabitatge-sotmpes-a-informacio-publica/pla-local-dhabitatge-ripollet-document-dexposicio-publica.pdf/@_@download/file/Pla%20Local%20d'Habitatge%20Ripollet.%20Document%20d'exposici%C3%B3%20p%C3%BAblica.pdf [Accessed on 20/06/2022]

¹⁵ European Commission (2020) European Entrepreneurial Regions: Regional ecosystem mapping: Region of Catalonia, May 2020, Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2775dfa2-ac57-11ea-bb7a-01aa75ed71a1> [Accessed on 21/10/2022]

¹⁶ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021) Ripollet Impulsa. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/ripollet-impulsa> [Accessed on 20/06/2022]

¹⁷ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022) L'Ajuntament endega un projecte per feminitzar el sector del metall i les instal·lacions. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/ajuntament/comunicacio/sala-de-premsa/notes-de-premsa/ocupacio-projecte-dona-metall> [Accessed on 22/11/2022]

(1,483) and Romania (1,431).¹⁸ Moroccan (59,181), Colombian (39,880) and Italian (29,446) are the main nationalities of migrants in Spain.¹⁹ The data does not fully represent the newcomer population, since it includes second generation migrants who were born in Spain but have not acquired Spanish citizenship.

A more detailed population estimate for Ripollet from the Catalan Statistical Institute indicates that 39,139 people lived there in 2021, including 6,307 foreign-born citizens and 4,835 foreign-born citizens with foreign citizenships. In Ripollet, immigration increased slowly but steadily between 2000 - 2020, except between 2013-16²⁰.

The municipality has no written data on migration changes over time, nor do they have information on migration waves. City council officials are aware of the lack of data and are working to develop a culture of data collection.

In an interview with a municipality team of councillors, it emerged that one main event shaped the relationship between Ripollet and migration: internal migration from the South of Spain to Ripollet in the 1960s. This was a crucial period in Ripollet's history because migration as well as xenophobia started to appear. The 1960s wave of migrants was the first one happening in Ripollet and the migrants involved in this wave faced discrimination: they were considered less developed. There was a derogatory term used to describe people who were not from Catalonia and came from elsewhere. Following that event, the level of discrimination for the Ripollet councillors decreased until we arrived at the present day. According to council members, the most significant changes in the city council in the last decade related to migrations have been facilitation of family reunification and paperwork. Other specific policies for migrants are not provided by the city council. In terms of migration policies, the municipality adheres to Spanish regulations.²¹

1.2.2 Civil society and migrant-led organisations in the municipality

Ripollet does not have formally registered migrant-run organizations, but several non-governmental organizations (NGOs) coordinate their work with the municipality to help and support migrants. The city council provides migrants registered in the municipality with information about organizations delivering housing, legal and social assistance. [Acollim Ripollet-Cerdanyola](#) is the most active and well-known NGO in Ripollet that provides primary assistance to migrants. The organization is open to everyone who wants to support NGOs working in the migration field. They work to channel the help that the

¹⁸ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022) Citizen service office. List of foreign nationals residing in the municipality (internal document).

¹⁹ Instituto Nacional de Estadística (2021) Cifras de Población (CP) a 1 de enero de 2022 Estadística de Migraciones (EM). Año 2021. Available at: https://www.ine.es/prensa/cp_e2022_p.pdf [Accessed on 20/10/2022]

²⁰ Statistical Institute of Catalonia (2021) Ripollet (Vallès Occidental). Available at: https://www.idescat.cat/emex/?id=081803&lang=en&utm_campaign=cercador&utm_medium=sugg&utm_source=Idescat&utm_term=ripollet&utm_content=emex [Accessed on 15/12/2022]

²¹ Interview with the municipality team of councillors. Date: 15-11-2022

people of Ripollet want to offer to migrants and refugees and, at the same time, support the rights of migrants and denounce European migration policies.

Community interaction is encouraged in other organizations like 'La Gresca', 'Escola d'Adults', and 'Oficina de Català'. Although migrants are not their intended audience, they nevertheless serve as a gathering place for them.

The [La Gresca Leisure Center](#) is a non-profit association working with children, young people, and families in the Pont Vell-Tiana and Quatre Cantons neighbourhood. In addition to assisting new residents, Gresca also supports people living alone in the area and teaches children and young people about democratic ideals, solidarity, and environmental responsibility.

The Generalitat de Catalonia's Department of Education owns the [Jaume Tuset Escola d'Adults \(Adult Training Center\)](#). This facility is located in the heart of the municipality and offers adult training opportunities, including to migrants and refugees.

[Oficina de Catala](#) is a language school which has the aim of facilitating the knowledge, use and dissemination of the Catalan language in all areas. Language schools are one of the arrival points for many migrants and refugees in Ripollet.

2 THE LOCAL GOVERNANCE AND MIGRATION AND DIVERSITY POLICY

2.1 Governance structure and local decision-making powers

The City Council is the main administration body for citizens of municipalities like Ripollet and its function is to govern and administer the interests of local residents. The Plenary Session of the City Council is the highest governing body in the council.

The City Council is made up of the Mayor and the Councillors elected in the municipal elections. The candidate with the absolute majority of votes is chosen by the council members as the Mayor for the term of four years.

Councillors are elected by secret universal suffrage²² as established by current regulations. The number of councillors to be elected in each municipality is determined by the number of inhabitants. In Ripollet, a municipality with population in the range of 20,000 to 50,000 inhabitants, there are 21 councillors in 2022.

The Mayor, who presides over the council, is the top political representative. He/she/they is elected from among the councillors of the plenary and appoints the Deputy Mayors who will replace him/her/them when required.

The governing team is made up of the Ara Decidim Ripollet municipal group, with 10 councillors. The Mayor is José M. Osuna López. The opposition is made up of the [PSC-CP](#)

²² Right to vote for all adult citizens.

municipal groups (6 councillors), *Ciutadans* (3 councillors), *SOM Ripollet* (1 councilor). The 10 councillors who make up the Ara Decidim Ripollet municipal group, chaired by the Mayor José M. Osuna López, include: Pilar Castillejo Medina, Reyes Muñoz Nevado, Meritxell Caler Vergara, Andrea Guijarro García, Sergio Linares Salgado, Oriol Mor Hernández and Éric Plata Fernández.

According to the regulations in force, the main functions of the Plenary are to: (1) Oversee and control the governing bodies; (2) Reach an agreement on participation in supra-municipal organizations; (3) Approve urban planning legislation's plans; (4) Give approval to the Municipal Organic Regulation; (5) Construct and manage complementary bodies; (6) Determine own tax resources, approve budgets and allocate expenses; (7) Set the amount of the complementary remuneration of the officials and the name and contingent staff regime; and (8) Exercise administrative and judicial actions.

2.2. Migration and integration policy

The City Council comprises six core departments of – Social Rights, Presidency, Governance, City and Sustainability, Employment, Business and Commerce, and Community Development.

Within the area of Social Rights, there are further departments, including the Department of Social Services, the ARE, the Department of Education, the Department of Housing, the Department of Local Police, and the Department of Equality and Life. Under the Equality and Life, there is also the Inclusion Department. Each department can exercise equal influence on the others and report on actions to be taken. Departments in Ripollet work together to ensure citizens' well-being.

The Department of Inclusion is made up of units that focus on migrant reception, provision of residential permit and provision of legal and social advice. The Inclusion Department collaborates with other departments such as the Department of Social Services, the Department of Feminism and LGBTQIA, and the Department of Employment to respond to different interrelated issues like employment, violence or family support.

The municipality collaborates with local associations, including Acolim Ripollet-Cerdanyola which primarily assists refugees and migrants arriving in Ripollet. The association serves as a point of entry for immigrants before and after they are directed to the municipality.

In 2018, Acolim Ripollet-Cerdanyola and other organizations in the area presented a motion to the town council of Ripollet to improve the registration of residency conditions of newcomers. Ripollet accepted the motion and implemented the changes, simplifying the registration of residency procedure. The Ripollet city council offers a plan that eases the integration of newcomers by simplifying particular procedures like residency registration, family support, assistance with administrative tasks, family reunion, or residence renewal. Ripollet now offers a residence policy that enables immigrants, refugees, and asylum seekers without social support, who are living on the streets, who

are occupying housing, or who lack personal identification to apply easily for a residency permit.²³

In terms of migration policy, Ripollet adheres to Spanish regulations.²⁴ No specific policies for migrants are provided by the city, although the Education plan, provided by the Educational Department, is a policy that indirectly affects the migrant population. The Educational Plan facilitates services for the study and comprehension of the Catalan language, as well as the integration of all newcomers into the educational system. Children and adolescents are integrated into the city's educational system as soon as they arrive, ensuring that their educational rights are protected from the start. Other services, such as after-school programs, are also promoted to newcomer families in order to facilitate their first steps in the municipality.²⁵

2.3 Diversity and equality policy

2.3.1 Commitment to equality, diversity and inclusion

In the 'Reglament de Participació'²⁶ policy document from 2021, Ripollet council explicitly communicates its commitment to promoting a city open to diversity and inclusion, and one that is against racism, homophobia, transphobia, sexism and violence. It uses different channels to communicate its vision, such as social media, council website, videos, a local TV channel and radio.

2.3.2 Strategy for promoting diversity and equal opportunities

In 2022, Ripollet council has been working on its inclusion and diversity policies for schools with the aim of incorporating sexual, gender, family and diversity education in the curriculum of all schools in the area²⁷.

On the occasion of the 'Gay pride' in Ripollet, which took place on the 29th of June 2022, the council representatives stated that "*The municipality aims to promote a transfeminist,*

²³ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2018). Reclamen papers per a tots els migrants per la situació d'extrema necessitat. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/28665>. [Accessed on 20/11/2022]

²⁴ Interview with the municipality team of councillors. Date: 15-11-2022

²⁵ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022). Uns 1400 infants i joves s'han beneficiat aquest curs de les accions del Pla Educatiu d'Entorn. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/uns-1400-infants-i-joves-shan-beneficiat-aquest-curs-de-les-accions-del-pla-educatiu-dentorn>. [Accessed on 20/11/2022]

²⁶ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021). Reglament de Participació. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view> [Accessed on 13/06/2022]

²⁷ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022). Ripollet se suma un any més a la reivindicació per l'alliberament i l'orgull LGTBI. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/ripollet-se-suma-un-any-mes-a-la-reivindicacio-per-l'alliberament-i-l'orgull-lgtbi>. [Accessed on 13/06/2022]

antifascist, and anti-racist city, where there is not a space for neoliberal policies but for human rights and diversity.”²⁸

Ripollet council promotes policies aiming to protect the LGBTQIA+ communities from discrimination at different levels. In addition to this, the municipality offers spaces of dialogue open to the community where trans groups can share their personal experiences and make visible the discrimination suffered in several areas of life. The municipality collaborates with the Observatory Against Homophobia to advance education in human rights principles and understanding of sexual and gender emotional diversity²⁹.

There is a Diversity and Equality plan for sexual, gender and sexual diversity³⁰ which describes the municipality's objective to promote cross-cutting feminist policies in education, health, sexual and reproductive rights, mobility, and housing. Migrants are not identified as a target group for the diversity and equality plan.

There is no explicit strategy for promoting diversity and equal opportunities for migrants in the city. Although, Ripollet encourages a new perspective on migration that emphasizes 'historical memory'. The municipality runs a number of educational initiatives that emphasize the value of advancing democracy and teaching about Ripollet's past with a focus on dictatorship, past migration, and violations of human rights. The City has a specific municipal memory programme entitled 'Memory = Dignity'³¹ started in 2018 with an aim to prevent human rights violation and to promote democracy through education about Ripollet's migration past. Every year, the city organizes an event where invited speakers present past human rights violations in the municipality, with a focus on Francisco Franco's dictatorship, the Spanish Civil War, and the migration waves to Spain and Mexico during 1939, when Francisco Franco established his power in the country.

The city has dedicated departments tackling different axes of inequality. Ripollet has a department working for the support of inhabitants facing gender and sexual

²⁸Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022). Manifest signat per l'Ajuntament de Ripollet i l'Observatori contra l'Homofòbia. Available at://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/politiques-lgtbi/diades-reivindicatives/dia-internacional-de-la-visibilitat-trans/manifest-2022. [Accessed on 22/06/2022]

²⁹Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022). Manifest signat per l'Ajuntament de Ripollet i l'Observatori contra l'Homofòbia. Available at://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/politiques-lgtbi/diades-reivindicatives/dia-internacional-de-la-visibilitat-trans/manifest-2022. [Accessed on 25/06/2022]

³⁰ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2018). Pla local d'igualtat per a la diversitat afectiva sexual i de gènere. Available at: <http://upload.ripollet.cat/FILES/PDF/ripollet-lgtbi-plalgtbi2018-2022.pdf>. [Accessed on 13/06/2022]

³¹ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2018). Presentació dels programes municipals de memòria "Memòria=Dignitat". Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/ajuntament/comunicacio/sala-de-premsa/notes-de-premsa/28181> [Accessed on 26/09/2022]

discrimination,³² and a department promoting equal political and social access to services for people with functional diversity.³³

2.3.3 Consideration of intersectionality

The municipality of Ripollet adopt an intersectional approach in all its areas of action. Intersectional feminism is considered by the municipality as the gaze to be used to structure policies, events and communication and dissemination strategies. People experiencing several intersecting forms of discrimination based, for example, on sexual identity, age and (in)ability find socio-legal support in the municipality thanks to the dedicated departments. The society of Ripollet is also involved in events promoting a higher consciousness on diversity and inclusion, mainly focusing on the LGBTQIA+ community, social and emotional learning, and gender-based discrimination and violence. The aim of the municipality is to work with people suffering discrimination, but also with the community perpetrating discrimination.³⁴

The municipality adopt the intersectional approach in different spheres of policy. Recognizing the challenges that people of various ages may face in our technological societies, the Education department of the city council organizes technology courses for people of various ages in collaboration with the *Associacion La Grasca*. This approach acknowledges the intersection of discrimination that older people may face. In 2022 and 2021, the city of Ripollet also began *Semana de la gen gran* a few days dedicated to the municipality's elderly residents, where they are invited to participate in participatory spaces of discussion, cine forum, and workshops.³⁵

Members of the municipality recently recognized the intersecting discrimination women face at work, at home, and in their social lives. These intersecting discriminations emerged in several participatory workshops on community needs conducted in the municipality of Ripollet that lead to co-thinking and co-creating of a community space for women 'Ca de la Dona'. Ca de La Dona is the response to these needs. The Feminism and LGBTQIA+ councillor Meritxell Caler Vergara, during the inauguration act, explained that "Ca de la Dona" is a co-created place where women: a) can receive psychological and social support; b) can join courses on entrepreneurship; c) can find a space to organize

³² Ajuntament de Ripollet. Feminismes. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/politiques-igtbi>

³³ Ajuntament de Ripollet. Dret Socials. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/seu-electronica/tramits/drets-socials>. [Accessed on 26/09/2022]

³⁴ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022). Manifest signat per l'Ajuntament de Ripollet i l'Observatori contra l'Homofòbia. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/politiques-igtbi/diades-reivindicatives/dia-internacional-de-la-visibilitat-trans/manifest-2022https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/politiques-igtbi/diades-reivindicatives/dia-internacional-de-la-visibilitat-trans/manifest-2022>. [Accessed on 13/06/2022]

³⁵ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022). Setmana de la gent gran. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/agenda/setmana-de-la-gent-gran-la-gran-marato>. [Accessed on 24/11/2022]

their events; d) can find an environment where they can feel safe³⁶. The space is intended to be open to all women in Ripollet, and the city council will implement several communication strategies, such as promoting events in different languages, organizing intercultural activities, to invite migrant women to participate in this new environment. At the time being, migrant women do not have a specific and dedicated space to meet.³⁷

In response to the Commission for Persons with Disabilities' request for a greater emphasis on accessibility in Ripollet, financial aids were established in October 2022 to assist all establishments that are planning or have already implemented reforms to ensure accessibility for all in their shops and activities.³⁸

Ripollet does not yet offer a service to address inequities brought on by migrant status but as stated during the first event held on the 30th of September 2022 on Migrant participation in Policymaking with Meritxell Caler Vergara, feminism and LGBTQIA+ councillor in Ripollet *"Thanks to the MILE project and the data analysis conducted, the municipality is now working on developing a service to tackle inequalities arising from migrant status, considering that newcomers make up 45% of the entire population"*.³⁹

In the municipality of Ripollet, migrants and refugees are not portrayed using a colonial perspective, and they are not stigmatized using stereotypical words or adjectives. In the municipality, a neutral legislative terminology is used. There is no victimization or stigmatization in the official documents, either of the municipality website and social media.

³⁶ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021). Es presenta el projecte del futur Espai Casa de la dona, l'equipament de referència feminista a Ripollet

Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/es-presenta-el-projecte-del-futur-espai-casa-de-la-dona-lequipament-de-referencia-feminista-a-ripollet>. [Accessed on 23/07/2022]

³⁷ Interview with the municipality team of councillors. Date: 15-11-2022

³⁸ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022). L'Ajuntament destina quasi 24.000 € a subvencionar millores d'accessibilitat a comerços, hostaleria i empreses. Available at:

<https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/lajuntament-destina-quasi-24000-e-a-subvencionar-millores-daccessibilitat-a-comerços-hostaleria-i-empreses>. [Accessed on 20/11/2022]

³⁹ Ripollet Radio (2022). Info Setmanal 565. Available at: <https://www.ripolletradio.cat/2022/09/15/info-setmanal-15-09-2022/>. [Accessed on 20/09/2022]

3 THE EVOLUTION OF INCLUSIVITY OF MIGRANTS IN POLICY MAKING

3.1 Migrant inclusion in local policy making

Data from council representative interviews and desk analysis of official council documents do not include information on migrant inclusion in local policymaking. It appears that civic participation of migrants has received little attention from Ripollet's local decision makers over the past decades. Nevertheless, the MILE project has provided an opportunity to improve council's engagement with migrant communities, as stated by the Feminism and LGBTQIA+ councillor Maritxell Caler, in the recent interview conducted with the local radio: *"the project MILE will allow us to find a way to connect more with the migrant communities, to discuss more with them, to include them in policymaking"*.⁴⁰

Since there has been no emphasis on migrant political participation and involvement in policymaking in previous decades, joining the MILE project aiming to foster inclusion of migrants in policymaking has been a significant change in the municipality.

The municipality of Ripollet has committed to promoting the inclusion of migrants in policymaking beginning in 2022 through the MILE project. As mentioned in the previous session, The Educational Plan⁴¹ under the Educational Department facilitates services for Catalan language study and comprehension, as well as the integration of all newcomers into the educational system. Children and adolescents are immediately integrated into the city's educational system, ensuring that their educational rights are protected from the start. Other services, such as after-school programs, are also promoted to newcomer families to help them get started in the community.

The key 'critical events' that have shaped the evolution of inclusivity of migrants in local policy-making in Ripollet are summarised below and further elaborated in table 1.

- **Migration in the 1960's:** In the 1960's, there was a massive movement of migrants, in search of better job conditions, from the South of Spain to the North of the country. A large number of people from Andalusia in particular reached Ripollet. Based on an interview conducted with migrants' organizations, Ripollet's first wave of migrants arrived during 1960, and xenophobia was first experienced by the migrant population around that time.
- **Western Sahara War (1975-1991) took place between 1975 and 1991.** Following this period, Spain, which colonized the region until 1975, began several assistance programmes. Several groups of citizens in Spain organized to support the Sahrawi population. During summer 2002, the Sahrawi Host Families Collective of Ripollet initiated a project to host children and youths from the Sahrawi region to offer

⁴⁰Ripollet Radio (2022). Info Setmanal 565. Available at: <https://www.ripolletradio.cat/2022/09/15/info-setmanal-15-09-2022/>. [Accessed on 20/09/2022]

⁴¹Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022). Uns 1400 infants i joves s'han beneficiat aquest curs de les accions del Pla Educatiu d'Entorn. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/ajuntament/comunicacio/sala-de-premsa/notes-de-premsa/comissio-pla-educatiu-entorn-ripollet-2021-2022>. [Accessed on 24/11/2022]

them support and assistance. Participating families hosted several young people aged 6-12 years in their homes during July and August. The children mostly came from refugee camps from Sahrawi region.⁴²

- **2015 - The Syrian war.** In the course of the Syrian war, the municipality organized two meetings with entities, political parties, and citizens to find ways to collaborate with the Syrian population. The result of these meetings was the organization of a space in the municipality for clothing collection for migrants to be sent to Syria and for the Syrian population reaching Spain.⁴³
- **2017:** During 2017, the National Campaign '*Casa nostra, casa vostra*' (Our home, your home) was launched around Spain by the organization *Casa nostra, casa vostra* to ask municipalities to promote the inclusion of refugees around the country.⁴⁴ In Ripollet, citizens organized a demonstration entitled 'We want to welcome' to encourage municipalities to prioritize the reception of refugees and migrants in their political agendas.⁴⁵
- **2017:** Ripollet has always encouraged historical memory and moments of reflection on the difficulties endured during Francisco Franco's dictatorship. *The Never Again Collective* organized on 28 August 2017 a walking route through Ripollet to discover the most important places in the municipality where refugees arrived during the Civil War and fascism.⁴⁶ Reflections on the connection between today's migration and past migration were presented during the event.
- **2018:** In 2018, *Acollim Ripollet-Cerdanyola* and other organizations in the area presented a motion to the town councils of Ripollet to improve the residency registration conditions of newcomers.⁴⁷ Following the organization's event, the process of registering in the municipality became simpler and more accessible to

⁴²Ajuntament de Ripollet (2002). Ripollet tornarà a acollir nens dels sahrauís aquest estiu. Available at:

<https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/940>. [Accessed on 20/09/2022]

⁴³ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2015). El Casal de Joves serà un punt de recollida de roba per als refugiats del 5 al 17 d'octubre

Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/22863>. [Accessed on 20/09/2022]

⁴⁴ Campaign organized by Casa Nostra Casa Vostra. The Non-Governmental Organization Casa Nostra Casa Vostra support citizens of Spain in organizing campaigns against migrant discrimination at various levels. Available at: <https://casanostracasavostra.com/amnistyforall/>. [Accessed on 19/11/2022]

⁴⁵ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2017). Suport a la manifestació 'Volem acollir' per a l'acollida de persones refugiades i migrants. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/25542> [Accessed on 19/11/2022]

⁴⁶ Ajuntament de Ripollet . Ruta a peu pels escenaris dels refugiats de la Guerra Civil #FMRipollet17. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/26592> [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

⁴⁷ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2018). Reclamen papers per a tots els migrants per la situació d'extrema necessitat. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/28665>. [Accessed on 20/11/2022]

all types of citizens. The municipal government listened to the needs expressed by the organization and worked on facilitating the process. Ripollet now offers a residence policy that enables immigrants, refugees, and asylum seekers without social support, who are living on the streets, who are occupying housing, or who lack personal identification to apply easily for a residency permit.⁴⁸

- **2021:** The 2021 *Reglament de Participació*⁴⁹ sets up various channels for citizen participation in the municipality, as well as rules for citizen engagement. The regulation is inspired by the Barcelona municipality's *Reglament de Participació*⁵⁰ published in 2017 to guarantee citizen participation in the metropolis of Barcelona. According to the interview with a Participation Councillor, the new regulation formalized informal spaces of participation and better defined the rules and steps to collect citizen feedback as well as for citizens to send instances.⁵¹
- **In March 2022:** Ripollet created an infographic to support Ukrainian refugees to “navigate” bureaucracy in neighbouring areas. Ripollet did not implement hosting policies, it mainly focused on communication and dissemination of information. There was no data collected by the city council regarding the number of Ukrainians who settled in Ripollet. Citizen participation in the city council became more formally organized.
- **July 2022:** On 24th of June 2022, 23 migrants were killed during a confrontation with Moroccan and Spanish security forces at the Melilla border fence. Conflict escalated as around 2,000 migrants gathered in the early hours of the morning to cross the border into Spain. Amnesty International has requested an investigation into migration policies between Morocco and Spain, citing human rights violations, abuse of power, and violence at the border.⁵² In July the 4th 2022, the entities *Acollim Cerdanyola-Ripollet* and *Unitat Contra el Feixisme i el Racisme (UCFR Cerdanyola i Ripollet)* organized a protest to denounce the violence against migrants and refugees trying to enter Spain through the borders of Morocco. Citizens of Ripollet organized an event in the municipality to show their solidarity with the migrants.
- **September 15th 2022:** The municipality of Ripollet together with Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona and Kudwa organization hosted the first participatory

⁴⁸ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2018). Reclamen papers per a tots els migrants per la situació d'extrema necessitat. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/28665>. [Accessed on 13/09/2022]

⁴⁹ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021), Reglament de Participació. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

⁵⁰ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021). Reglament de Participació. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view> [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

⁵¹ Interview with the Participation Councillor. 18-11-2022

⁵² Amnesty International (2022). Melilla Never Again. Available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2022/06/melilla-never-again/>. [Accessed on 24/11/2022]

event on [Participatory Inclusive Democracy](#) aiming to create a space of discussion between migrants living in Ripollet and researchers, activists, policymakers and NGOs working in the field of advocacy and policymaking. Several stakeholders, including migrants, NGOs and policymakers met for the first time in the municipality to discuss migrant inclusion in policymaking.

Table 1 Migrant inclusion in local policy making: timeline of progress in the municipality of Ripollet

When	Global event	National event	Local event	Impact
1960's		Internal migration flows in Spain. In 1960, a significant movement of migrants from the South to the North of Spain takes place, many in search of better jobs.	Arrival of internal migrants to Ripollet. Throughout the 1960's, a significant a number of people from Andalusia move to Ripollet.	Internal migration impact in Ripollet. Ripollet experiences the first wave of migrants reaching the municipality. First acts of xenophobia are experienced by the migrant population. ⁵³
2002		Aftermath of Western Sahara War. Following the war period, (1975–1991), Spain which colonized the Western Sahara region until 1975 began several assistance programmes, involving groups of citizens organised to support the Sahrawi population.	Establishing Sahrawi Host Families Collective. The Sahrawi Host Families Collective ⁵⁴ of Ripollet hosted several young people from 6 to 12 years old in their homes during July and August of 2002. The children mostly come from refugee camps from Sahrawi region. ⁵⁵	Welcoming Sahrawi refugees in Ripollet. Families in Ripollet organized themselves to offer support to Sahrawi families.
2015	The Syrian refugee crisis. The Syrian refugee crisis is the largest refugee crisis in		Supporting refugee welcome campaign. In 2015, the Ripollet Municipality organises two	Supporting Syrian refugees. The result of these meetings organised

⁵³ Source: Interviews with associations working with migrants in Ripollet, 15 November 2022.

⁵⁴ During the summer break, this organization aimed to host Sahrawi children and families. The organization does not currently exist.

⁵⁵ **Ajuntament de Ripollet (2002) 'Ripollet tornarà a acollir nens dels sahrauís aquest estiu', Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/940>. [Accessed on 20/09/2022]**

	history. More than 6.8 million Syrians have been forced to flee Syria between 2011-2022. ⁵⁶		meetings with entities, political parties and neighbours to collaborate with the Syrian population. The assembly at the Cultural Centre decides on the final destination of the money collected during the Refugees Welcome campaign. ⁵⁷	by Ripollet Municipality is the organization of a space in the municipality for clothing collection for refugees to be sent to Syria and for the Syrian population reaching Spain. ⁵⁸
2017		National campaign to welcome migrants and refugees. During 2017, a national campaign 'Casa nostra, casa vostra' (Our home, your home) is launched around Spain by the organization of the same name to ask municipalities to promote refugee inclusion around the country. ⁵⁹	Organising a demonstration in support of welcoming migrants. In Ripollet, citizens organise a demonstration titled 'We want to welcome' to encourage municipalities to prioritize the reception of refugees and migrants in their political agendas. ⁶⁰	Welcoming migrants in Ripollet. Ripollet residents join the national call for proper reception of migrants in Spanish cities.
2017			Reflecting on the migration past. On 28 August 2017, the 'Mai	Reviving the memory of historical migration.

⁵⁶ UNHCR (2022) 'Syria Refugee Crisis Explained', The UN Refugee Agency, 8 July 2022, Available at: <https://www.unrefugees.org/news/syria-refugee-crisis-explained/> [Accessed on 21/11/2022]

⁵⁷ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2015) 'Nova assemblea sobre l'ajuda als refugiats sirians', Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/23073>
<https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/23073>

⁵⁸ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2015) 'El Casal de Joves serà un punt de recollida de roba per als refugiats del 5 al 17 d'octubre', Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/22863>. [Accessed on 20/09/2022]

⁵⁹ Campaign organized by Casa Nostra Casa Vostra. The Non-Governmental Organization Casa Nostra Casa Vostra support citizens of Spain in organizing campaigns against migrant discrimination at various levels. Available at: <https://casanostracasavostra.com/amnistyforall/>. [Accessed on 19/11/2022]

⁶⁰ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2017) 'Suport a la manifestació 'Volem acollir' per a l'acollida de persones refugiades i migrants', Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/25542> [Accessed on 19/11/2022]

			Més' (Never Again Collective) ⁶¹ organise a walking route through Ripollet to discover the most important places in the municipality where refugees arrived during the Civil War and fascism. ⁶²	Ripollet has always encouraged historical memory and moments of reflection on the difficulties endured during Francisco Franco's dictatorship. Intense work has been done in the municipality to draw connections between historical and present migration.
2018			Calling for newcomer registration. In 2018, 'Acollim Cerdanyola-Ripollet' (We welcome Cerdanyola Ripollet), an NGO that supports migrants in Ripollet, and other organizations in the area, present a motion to the council to facilitate the registration of newcomers and improve their access to basic rights and services. ⁶³	Improving the registration of newcomers. The municipal government listens to the calls from NGOs to make the registration process in the municipality easier and more accessible for all types of citizens.
2020			Criticising refugee camp conditions. On 19 October 2020, several NGOs, including 'Acollim	Crowdfunding for Lesbos refugee camp. 'Acció Solidaria i Logística'

⁶¹ Mai Més is a project that aims to organise events in municipalities throughout Catalonia to discuss and make people aware of deportation, historical memory, and dictatorship in the past. Available at: <https://xarxamimes.org/>. [Accessed on 23/11/2022]

⁶² Ajuntament de Ripollet. Ruta a peu pels escenaris dels refugiats de la Guerra Civil #FMRipollet17. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/26592> [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

⁶³ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2018) 'Reclamen papers per a tots els migrants per la situació d'extrema necessitat', Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/28665>. [Accessed on 20/11/2022]

			Cerdanyola-Ripollet' (We welcome Cerdanyola Ripollet) and 'Acció Solidaria i Logística' (Solidarity Action and Logistics) denounce the situation in the new refugee camp on the Greek island of Lesbos where thousands of refugees were left without basic supplies, such as water. ⁶⁴	(Solidarity Action and Logistics) launches a crowdfunding campaign to raise money to be sent to Lesbos in Greece.
2021			Introducing civic participation regulation. The 'Reglament de Participació' ⁶⁵ is a document, introduced by Ripollet Council in 2021, that defines different channels for citizen participation as well as Ripollet's commitment to promote diversity and inclusion. The regulation is inspired by the 'Reglament de Participació' ⁶⁶ published in 2017 by Barcelona municipality.	Formalising civic participation structures. Citizen participation in the city council becomes more formally organised. There were several spaces for participation prior to this new regulation, but they were mostly informal and unstructured. The new regulation promotes participation of citizens from diverse cultural and gender backgrounds, though without explicit mention of migrants.

⁶⁴ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2020) 'Acollim Cerdanyola-Ripollet demana ajuda per a una potabilitzadora al camp de refugiats de Lesbos', Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/32395>. [Accessed on 23/11/2022]

⁶⁵ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021) 'Reglament de Participació', Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

⁶⁶ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021) 'Reglament de Participació', Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

<p>2022</p>	<p>The war in Ukraine. In February 2022, Russia invades Ukraine. Nearly a third of Ukrainian population were forced to flee their homes.⁶⁷</p>	<p>Catalonia’s support for Ukrainian refugees. The Catalonia government website⁶⁸ launches a page in support of Ukrainian refugees. The webpage provides information on how to host families and promote language support.</p>	<p>Communicating support for refugees. In March 2022, the Ripollet Council creates an infographic to support Ukrainian refugees to ‘navigate’ bureaucracy in neighbouring areas. Ripollet did not implement hosting policies; it mainly focused on communication and dissemination of information⁶⁹.</p>	<p>Facilitating refugee integration. In response to the Ukraine refugee crisis, the Ripollet Council decides to facilitate refugees’ integration and understanding of the municipality’s and neighbouring municipalities’ policies.</p>
<p>2022</p>			<p>Introducing new civic participation plans. Six new plans or projects are introduced in Ripollet as a result of implementing the local participation regulation.⁷⁰</p>	<p>Co-creating civic participation projects. Participatory processes introduced through the new civic participation regulation have resulted in six co-created projects in Ripollet: (1) The Local Housing Plan; (2) The feminist policies plan; (3) The Plan of assistance for the elderly in Ripollet; (4) Ripollet’s new municipal management</p>

⁶⁷ United Nations (2022) ‘The UN and the war in Ukraine: key information’, 9 March 2022, Available at: <https://unric.org/en/the-un-and-the-war-in-ukraine-key-information/> [Accessed on 09/12/2022]

⁶⁸ Ajuntament de Barcelona (2022) ‘Catalonia stands with Ukraine / Каталонія разом з Україною’, Available at: <https://web.gencat.cat/en/ucraina/>. [Accessed on 15/12/2022]

⁶⁹ Ajuntament de Barcelona (2022) ‘Infografia amb informació útil sobre persones refugiades d’Ucraïna’, Available at: https://www.ripollet.cat/ajuntament/comunicacio/solidaritat-amb-ucraina/infografia_informacio_util_ucraina-acm-1.pdf/view. [Accessed on 15/12/2022]

⁷⁰ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021) ‘Reglament de Participació’, Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

				model for drinking water service; (5) A new Casal d'Avis model (House For grandfathers); and (6) A new model for establishing Municipal Culture and Sports Councils. ⁷¹
2022		Confrontation on the Spanish border. On 24 June 2022, 23 migrants are killed during a confrontation with Moroccan and Spanish security forces at the Melilla border fence. The conflict escalated as around 2,000 migrants gathered to cross the border into Spain. Amnesty International has requested an investigation into migration policies between Morocco and Spain, citing human rights violations, abuse of power, and violence at the border. ⁷²	Criticising violence against migrants. On 4 July 2022, the NGOs 'Acollim Cerdanyola-Ripollet' and 'Unitat Contra el Feixisme i el Racisme' (UCFR Cerdanyola i Ripollet) organise a protest to denounce the violence against migrants and refugees trying to enter Spain through the borders of Morocco.	Standing in solidarity with migrants. Citizens of Ripollet organise an event in the municipality to show their solidarity with the migrants affected by the confrontation on the Spanish border.
2022			Promoting migrants' civic participation. On 15 September 2022, the municipality of Ripollet together with Universitat	Discussing migrant inclusion in decision-making. Several stakeholders, including

⁷¹ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022) 'Processos Participatius tancats', Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/processos-participatius/processos-tancats>. [Accessed on 15/12/2022]

⁷² Amnesty International (2022) 'Melilla Never Again', Available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2022/06/melilla-never-again/>. [Accessed on 24/11/2022]

			Autonoma de Barcelona and Kudwa organization host the first participatory event on Participatory Inclusive Democracy aiming to create a space of discussion between migrants living in Ripollet and researchers, activists, policymakers and NGOs working in the field of advocacy and policymaking. ⁷³	migrants, NGOs and policymakers meet for the first time in the Ripollet municipality to discuss migrant inclusion in local policymaking.
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⁷³ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2022) 'The CIP Molí d'en Rata hosts a round table on inclusive democratic participation focused on migrants and refugees', 17 September 2022, Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/el-cip-moli-den-rata-acull-una-taula-rodona-sobre-la-participacio-democratica-inclusiva-centrada-en-les-persones-migrades-i-refugiades> [Accessed on 09/12/2022]

3.2 Best practice example of migrant inclusion in policy making

There are currently no best practice examples for migrant inclusion in policymaking to present. Ripollet's city council is interested in developing new procedures and approaches to begin facilitating migrants' inclusion in policymaking by the end of 2023. This new approach will be established through the MILE project.

4 ENGAGEMENT OF MIGRANT COMMUNITIES IN POLICY MAKING

4.1 City strategy for local participation

4.1.1 Does the city have an explicitly written strategy to promote participation by residents in public decision making irrespective of their nationality / background?

Ripollet has a long history of local civic participation, which began in 1980 when the municipality established three municipal councils for local participation: the cultural council, the work council, and the sports council. Additionally, the school council and the social service council were created afterwards. All these groups were established as spaces for the population to discuss five specific themes: the management of culture, work, sport, school and social services in the municipality.

The Reglament de Participació⁷⁴ is a document developed in 2021 that defines different channels for citizen participation. The regulation is inspired by the *Reglament de Participacio*⁷⁵ published in 2017 by Barcelona municipality.

The Reglament de Participació does not include any information about participation of migrants. The document states that:

- The entire population of Ripollet is invited to participate in the dedicated moments for citizen participation and that cultural diversity and a gender perspective should always be promoted.
- Themes such as policy changes and policy implementation can be promoted
- The participatory process has 4 phases:
 - Communicate the information to the people who can participate
 - Contribution of proposals and deliberation
 - Evaluation of the proposals
 - Assessment and planning

⁷⁴ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021), Reglament de Participació. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

⁷⁵ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021). Reglament de Participació. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

Citizen participation is seen by the municipality as fundamental to guarantee that the city is a safe space for everyone, and a context where several needs are addressed. To guarantee the participation of several collectives, including those that are underrepresented or stigmatized, is one of the objectives of Ripollet council.

4.1.2 Does the strategy commit to (1) making this a two-way process of communication; (2) responding to the voice of residents; and (3) giving voice to informal participatory action as well as formal processes such as consultations?

Yes. The municipality organizes round table participatory discussions on different social themes open to diverse social groups, such as elders, animal rights activists, feminists, LGTBTI+ members and people with disabilities.⁷⁶ In 2022, there is no round table on migrant integration in policy-making, but the municipality is considering creating one as a result of the MILE investigation.

Other channels for sharing data and information about local participation include WhatsApp groups for collective instances, online consultation platforms, and newspaper advertisements. The platforms/approaches to be used to reach the population are determined by the target group that the municipality wishes to reach.

4.1.3 Does the strategy adopt an intersectional approach seeking to tackle multiple axes of inequality simultaneously to promote local participation? Are some axes of inequality considered as principal?

The Policy on Citizen Participation does not mention intersectionality, but it does describe the goal of reaching and including a diverse group of participants in each space of discussion, as well as ensuring a non-discriminatory and stigmatized approach.

4.1.4 Is the intersectional approach to local participation adopted across different policy spheres?

As mentioned above, intersectionality is not conceptually defined in the policy on Citizen Participation but the goal of the document is to involve everyone in the participation process across different spheres such as education, health, schooling and housing. The document states that participation of members of different socio-cultural groups should be promoted and emphasized.

4.1.5 Does the city have any existing structures for political / civic participation of the local migrant population?

The municipality does not have any specific structures for political and civic participation of the local migrant population. However, the civic participation events in general are extended to the entire population and all Ripollet citizens are invited.

⁷⁶ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021). Reglament de Participació. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

4.2 Leadership, communication and coordination of participation

4.2.1 *Do decision makers actively promote participation of residents irrespective of their nationality?*

Yes. *Ara Decidim Ripollet*, the actual political party, established a new system to regularize participatory spaces in the municipality, defined in detailed in the *Reglament de Participació*.⁷⁷ Citizen participation is promoted as a pillar of the party's political programme. They publicise the participation calls through various channels, including the website, social media, WhatsApp groups, as well as the local newspaper and flyers distributed throughout the city.

4.2.2 *Does the city use migrant-specific communication channels to make the case for participation among (and to reach) migrant communities? What communication channels are used to make the case for participation? How are residents informed about the possibility to participate? Does the city use diverse communication methods to inform residents about the possibility to participate?*

The municipality benefits from the help of associations working with migrants such as *Acollim Ripollet* to reach migrant communities and involve them in participatory actions. Informally, associations inform the municipality about instances and needs through phone calls or emails. In the last 10 years, migrants in the area did not show interest in joining participatory spaces.⁷⁸ Residents in Ripollet are informed about upcoming events, including any opportunities to shape local policy, through social media channels, the council website, flyers distributed in their area, and a monthly local newspaper where all the scheduled events are reported.

Several communication methods are used, including digital and social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, local TV channel, and the Ripollet Radio, as well as more traditional ones, such as sending newspapers or flyers with upcoming events to residents' homes.

4.2.3 *Is intersectionality considered in communication?*

Yes, for example, by: (1) Promoting communication at two different levels, such as, using traditional methods that are more familiar for older people and more technological ones for the younger generation, taking into account different needs and perspectives; and (2) Promoting a non-discriminatory and non- stereotypical language in the Communication and Dissemination material to increase participation of unrepresented groups and generally excluded minorities.

⁷⁷ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021). *Reglament de Participació*. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>

⁷⁸ Source: Interviews with associations working with migrants in Ripollet. 15-11-2022

4.2.4 Does the city communicate the results of consultations to residents? How are the results of a consultation process and its responses communicated to residents?

The result of each consultation is reported on the Ripollet council website and shared by post in the monthly newspaper. Ripollet municipality's commitment is to allow everyone to be informed about the municipality life.

4.2.5 Does the city produce information about consultations in different languages? Who produces the information and in which languages is it provided?

Consultations are produced in two languages: Catalan and Castellano (Spanish). Information is not produced in any other languages.

4.2.6 Is there a coordination mechanism in place to ensure that participation of all residents is actively promoted and communicated effectively?

Internal proposal (from the Department of the municipality): The city has the Participation Councillor who collects instances from across councils in the municipality (for example from the department of Education, Health or Sports), evaluates them and promotes their diffusion or elimination. Departments make a proposal to the participatory department which evaluates the proposal and asks for feedback from the citizens. As part of citizen participation process, ideas, perceptions, and feedback are collected over a period of 30 days. The department develops a dissemination strategy that depends on the target to be reached (for elders, information is shared in newspapers or sent by post, for young people, web applications and Whatsapp are used for communication). A technical analysis of the proposal is then to be conducted by the municipality within two months. Through events, the results of the evaluation are presented to citizens. It is the responsibility of the departments involved in the proposal to guarantee that they will contribute to every stage of the participatory process.⁷⁹

External proposal (from citizens to the Department of the municipality): Individuals and organizations can submit proposals to the municipality via the web or in person. The Department that receives the proposal has responsibility for handling it, and ultimately recommending it to the Participation Councillor. After that, the process is the same as described above.

4.3 Equal access

4.3.1 Does the city use diverse platforms to enable participation? Do all residents have an equal chance to make their voices heard?

Yes. The city uses diverse platforms to enable participation through both informal and formal consultations, citizen forums, online questionnaires, round table discussions and a monthly newspaper about the activities happening in Ripollet.

⁷⁹ Interview with the Participation Councillor. 18-11-2022

4.3.2 Can migrants, refugees and asylum seekers access these platforms taking into account their specific circumstances?

The diverse platforms take into account the different financial situation people have to enable participation. They are mainly free to use, but do not consider the several languages spoken in the area. This lack of focus on languages may decrease local participation of refugees and asylum seekers that may not understand the purpose of an event, its objectives and targets.

4.3.3 Are these diverse platforms of participation proactively communicated to diverse groups of residents? Is it visible and known to all communities how they can participate? Are their specific concerns considered?

The municipality has established a TV and a radio channel to “reduce the social and political distance” with the population. These two channels are used to share stories of inhabitants of the area, news, and information about events, and round table discussions with the aim of promoting inhabitants' participation in socio-cultural-political spaces.⁸⁰

In the participatory spaces, all ideas and inputs are considered. Inputs and perspectives from vulnerable groups, such as elders, people who have experienced gender-based violence, and members of the LGBTQIA+ community, people with disabilities are welcomed and thoroughly examined since these are generally difficult to reach collectives.⁸¹

4.4 Institutional links and responsiveness

4.4.1 Is there a fully established mechanism in place to ensure that public institutions respond and incorporate the migrant voice in their decision making processes?

No, the municipality does not directly offer an established mechanism to incorporate migrant voices in the decision-making processes, although indirectly the Reglament de Participació⁸² stated that cultural diversity and a gender perspective should always be assured in every participatory event. This means that the perspectives of several cultural groups living in the municipality should be present in each participatory event.

4.4.2 Are migrants consulted on key policy spheres such as housing, education, health and employment? On which issues are migrants consulted?

No, migrants are not consulted on key policy spheres such as hosting, education, health and employment. They are not directly consulted in these policy spheres. There are no

⁸⁰ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021). Reglament de Participació. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

⁸¹ Interview with the Participation Councillor. 18-11-2022

⁸² Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021). Reglament de Participació. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

organized groups in the municipality, therefore needs of migrants and refugees did not reach the municipality.

4.4.3 To what degree are migrants represented in the city's consultative bodies, committees and issue-based groups? Are migrants involved in consultative bodies for key policy spheres?

Migrants are not directly involved in consultative bodies for key policy spheres in the municipality, and are not represented in the city's consultative bodies. To speed up this process, the municipality decided to participate in this project, as mentioned in several sections.

4.4.4 Can migrants set their own agenda or are the issues pre-selected by the local authority?

Everyone in the municipality, according to the Reglament de Participació⁸³, can add his/her/their agenda to the one pre-selected by the local authority. To do so, citizens must first register with the Register of Citizen Participation, which can be found in the Regulation on Citizen Participation, then write their request and submit it to the municipality via an online application. The request will be evaluated by the Participation Councillors, along with other councillors involved in the instance, and citizens will be notified of any changes to the agenda, if they occur.

4.4.5 Are provisions in place to ensure that participation structures, such as consultative bodies, can feed into the mainstream policy process of relevant public authorities and get a considered and timely response?

The municipality currently lacks participation structures such as consultative bodies. Informal "tables of discussion" are being held in the municipality to discuss and evaluate specific needs. There is a table discussion about Feminism taking place presently, but there is no formal procedure in place to make this table discussion feed into the mainstream policy process. Through the MILE project, the municipality intends to create a defined structure to ensure that participation structures can feed into the mainstream policy process.

4.5 Support for community self-organisation

4.5.1 Does the city administration work with migrant associations?

The council collaborates with the association **Acollim Ripollet-Cerdanyola Cerdanyola**: a citizen platform open to everyone who wants to support NGOs working in reception services for migrants, such as legal advice, housing and employment. They work to channel the help that the people of Ripollet want to offer to refugees and at the same time to claim the rights of migrants and denounce European migration policies. Migrant run organizations are not registered in the area.

⁸³ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021). Reglament de Participació. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

4.5.2 Does the city administration support the self-organisation of migrant communities?

According to the Regulation on Citizen Participation, the city administration supports self-organization in general, but does not target specifically the self-organization of migrant communities. Ripollet intends to establish new methodologies to motivate and support migrants' self-organization through the MILE project.⁸⁴

4.5.3 Are there funds or other support for organisational capacity building targeting migrants? Where does the funding come from and how sustainable are these funds in longer term?

The municipality of Ripollet does not offer organisational capacity building support targeting migrants, but it is planning to do so in collaboration with the association Kudwa as part of the MILE project. The aim will be to understand the needs and requests of the migrant communities living in Ripollet.

4.5.4 Does the city administration support intercultural dialogue and exchange between communities?

The city does not offer support for intercultural dialogue, but it focuses more on intergenerational dialogue. As mentioned in the previous section, Ripollet, through events and social activities, aims to foster historical awareness. It has several programmes focusing on migration experienced by Spanish migrants leaving Spain to escape from Francisco Franco and recent migrants. The goal of these moments of dialogue is to recognize similarities, and deconstruct prejudices and stereotypical images.

4.6 Monitoring quality of participation schemes

4.6.1 Does the city work with residents to improve activities promoted by its participation strategy at all levels, and to make it more effective?

The municipality of Ripollet has a specific page⁸⁵ on the municipality website to promote the activities done by all the organizations of the area. The page is divided into themes: Feminism, Culture, Environment, Sports, Neighbours, Education, Entrepreneurs, Social services and Religions. The municipality during the last 2 years has shown a commitment to supporting the development of new organizations promoting their events and activities, and facilitating their setting up.

4.6.2 Is there regular monitoring and evaluation of these participation activities?

The Ripollet municipality evaluates and reports the degree of involvement, the key concerns that have surfaced, and the upcoming meetings presented in the participation activities. The municipality distributes to the entire community and post on social media and on the municipality website all the evaluation and monitoring activities. The Participation Councillor reported that over the last five years, an average of 30-40 people

⁸⁴ Interview with the municipality team of councillors

⁸⁵ Ajuntament de Barcelona (2021). Directori d'associacions. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/ciutat/directori-dassociacions>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

have joined each participation space. These spaces lacked diversity, because always the “same people” joined these spaces. The city's goal is to increase local participation and promote alternative communication channels. There are no qualitative data collected on the perceptions of residents toward participatory spaces.⁸⁶

4.6.3 Are the results of monitoring and evaluation publicised, and do they feed back into the process?

As previously indicated, the results are posted on the various communication channels that the municipality provides, and citizens can give feedback if they do not recognize the data or if they wish to add to it. It is necessary to be enrolled in the Register of Citizen Participation in order to send feedback. So far, no qualitative feedback on the quality of civic participation has been gathered. According to the Participation Councillor, there are insufficient funds to conduct an adequate analysis.⁸⁷

4.6.4 What mechanism is in place to check the procedures and impact of participation schemes on a regular basis?

Currently, there is no mechanism in place to monitor the procedures and impact of participation schemes. No impact evaluation is taking place before and after the participatory spaces. The municipality's Participation Councillor stated that this is due to a lack of funds and possibilities.⁸⁸

4.6.5 How are changes to the participation schemes being decided?

Each event for local participation has its own rules based on the General Participation Document. These rules are approved by the municipality councillors. It is always possible for the public to share their thoughts and ideas after the local participation event. It is possible to participate in the local events as an individual or as part of an organised group.

4.7 Resources for participation

4.7.1 Is the value of participation in public decision making by all communities recognised by the city?

Yes. Ripollet prioritizes citizen participation. There is a desire to understand the desires and requirements of all different kinds of citizens. The municipality claims that Ripollet should be shaped by the needs and perspectives of all of its residents.⁸⁹

4.7.2 Is there adequate budgeting for staff time and training to support and facilitate residents' participation?

⁸⁶ Interview with the Participation Councillor. 18-11-2022

⁸⁷ Interview with the Participation Councillor. 18-11-2022

⁸⁸ Interview with the Participation Councillor. 18-11-2022

⁸⁹ Interview with the Participation Councillor. 18-11-2022

Yes. A specific part of the municipality budget is allocated to fostering participation in different areas. The person in charge of citizen participation in the municipality⁹⁰ - the Participation Councillor - coordinates proposals from other departments, evaluates them, organizes participatory spaces with citizens for feedback, evaluates the entire proposal and finally approves it.

4.7.3 Are grant programmes used to support residents in creating stable, inclusive activities and structures that can strengthen civic and political participation for the long term?

Yes. After postponing the 2020 call due to the pandemic, Ripollet City Council is starting Participatory Budgets again this year (2022). Participatory budgets are funds for participatory projects that citizens collectively aim to promote in the municipality. Anyone in the city over the age of sixteen is welcome to participate. Up to five investment projects will be implemented with a maximum budget of 200,000 euros.⁹¹

The European project MILE, in which Ripollet is involved, is also a grant-funded project aimed at increasing participation. MILE in fact promotes migrant participation in the municipality through research, capacity building, and policy implementation.

4.7.4 Which resources does the city invest in provisions for participation?

The municipality has a budget for participation handled by the Participation Department. Each department of the municipality also has a budget for participation in its specific field (for example, a participation budget for the Education department). The participation department coordinates its work with all other departments.⁹²

4.7.5 Are training opportunities for participants in place?

Different events were organized by the municipality to explain the functions of the Reglament de Participació in 2021, collecting citizen feedbacks and inputs. Training opportunities are taking place as part of the MILE project to facilitate the civic participation of migrants.

4.7.6 Is there a secretariat or a similar support structure to support participants?

Every participatory space where citizens can express their opinions and feedback is moderated by several councillors whose area of expertise is similar to the request/project being discussed by the municipality.

4.8 Commitment to full political rights for all residents

⁹⁰ Ajuntament de Ripollet (2021), Reglament de Participació. Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/serveis/participacio/el-reglament-de-participacio/ripollet-reglamentparticipacio.pdf/view>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

⁹¹ Ajuntament de Ripollet. L'Ajuntament de Ripollet obre els Pressupostos Participatius a tota la ciutadania, Available at: <https://www.ripollet.cat/actualitat/noticies/lajuntament-de-ripollet-obre-els-pressupostos-participatius-a-tota-la-ciutadania>. [Accessed on 28/10/2022]

⁹² Interview with the Participation Councillor. 18-112022

4.8.1 Does the city actively lobby for granting / extending full local voting rights to their migrant population?

No, the city does not currently actively lobby for granting or extension of full local voting rights to their migrant population. The municipality has not viewed the local migrant population as a target of political participation in recent decades, although the MILE project is seen as an opportunity to focus more on this collective, with wider implications for civic participation in the municipality.⁹³

4.8.2 What channels does the city use to make the case for extended political rights?

In 2022, the city does not make the case for extended political rights for migrants. The municipality sees the MILE project as an opportunity to collect, study, and understand the needs of migrants, especially since the municipality will hold elections next year, and changes can certainly be written and promoted in the new political programmes.⁹⁴

⁹³ Interview with the municipality team of councillors. 15-11-2022

⁹⁴ Interview with the municipality team of councillors. 15-11-2022

REFERENCES⁹⁵

Eurocities / Migration Work (2014) *Integrating Cities Toolkit: Engagement of migrant communities in local policy making processes and political participation.*

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Garcés-Masareñas, B. and R. Penninx (2016) *Integration Processes and Policies in Europe: Contexts, Levels and Actors*, Springer Open (eBook)

Igualtats Connect (2019) *Toolkit to incorporate intersectionality into local policies.*

⁹⁵ The research conducted as part of this project was informed by these sources, providing a framework for evaluating existing integration, equality, diversity and civic participation policy and practice.

APPENDIX – List of primary data sources

1. Interview with the municipality team of councillors, 15 November 2022
2. Interviews with associations working with migrants in Ripollet, 15 November 2022
3. Interview with the Participation Councillor, 18 November 2022